

M.M.A. Hendriksen, Review of Fenneke Sysling, *De Onmeetbare Mens. Schedels, ras, en wetenschapsgeschiedenis in Nederlands-Indië*. (Nijmegen: Vantilt, 2015). *Studium*, 8 (4), (pp. 233-235).

In early 2016, Fenneke Sysling gained a PhD at the Free University of Amsterdam with a thesis entitled *The archipelago of difference. Physical anthropology in the Netherlands East Indies, ca. 1890-1960*. Subsequently she decided not only to publish an academic monograph in English based on this thesis (forthcoming 2016), but also a popular science book in Dutch, *Immeasurable man*. The book is divided into six chapters, each discussing certain aspects of physical anthropology in the Dutch East-Indies between roughly 1890 and 1960, like collecting practices in the colony and the shipping of human remains to the Netherlands, the practices of measuring, photographing and casting living bodies, as well as the on-going confusion about the measurability of the human body and the significance of physical anthropology as a discipline. Well written and to the point, the book is a good introduction to a thorny topic.

The vast difference in available sources for the various periods and actors discussed results in some unevenness in its narrative. The first chapter, on early collecting practices, is necessarily based on scarce accounts of expeditions and provenance, which sometimes results in a slightly dry enumeration of facts. This forms a stark contrast with the other chapters, which have a much more fluent narrative structure. In chapter five, which discusses the life and career of J.P. Kleiweg de Zwaan (1875-1971) and the heydays of physical anthropology, we find a level of detail and insight into the persona of the protagonist that is absent from other chapters. This might be explained from the fact that family members of Kleiweg de Zwaan provided the author with anecdotes and archival materials unavailable for others in the book. Yet this chapter also raises questions that remain unanswered: why did Kleiweg de Zwaan retire in 1939, and what did the Dutch physical anthropologists do and what did they *not* do during World War II? Sysling suggests that they, for the largest part, disagreed with German race theory, but she only devotes a couple of lines to this. She probably did not want to stray too far from her main topic, but it is a subject that deserves more attention nonetheless.

For the non-specialist unfamiliar with the history of physical anthropology this will be a pleasing read, yet the very brief and general discussion of the historical context and continuing study of physical anthropology's central queries in the introduction and conclusion raise nagging questions that remain unanswered. Why for example do we learn nothing about similar practices in that other former colony on the other side of the world, Surinam? Brief snippets suggest that Dutch physical anthropology fitted into an international field of research, but were its methods and outcomes in any way exceptional, especially when compared to those of other colonizers? The moral issues surrounding physical anthropology linger in the background throughout the book, without being addressed explicitly. But if genetic research is indeed the successor of physical anthropology, as the conclusion suggests, what have its practitioners learned from the mistakes of their predecessors? A professional historian does not need to take on the role of the ethicist, yet in a book aimed at the general public a brief discussion of contemporary ethical codes and issues in genetic research and some suggestions for further reading, like Rebecca Skloot's *The Immortal Life of Henrietta Lacks*, which has also been translated to Dutch, would not have been out of place.

Overall, this book does what the title promises: it sketches a very readable, well-researched historical picture of physical anthropology in the Dutch East Indies for a general audience, without answering any of the bigger questions that play along in the background. Hopefully it will be successful enough for a second edition, in which some minor grammatical and typographical errors can be corrected. Sysling received a NWO Veni grant last year for four years of research on the 'quantified self': the history of self-tracking and self-monitoring from the weighing scales of nineteenth century playgrounds to the 'digital self' – another excellent topic for a popular science monograph.

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